

LEXICAL MISUSE IN ESSAYS WRITTEN BY UZBEK EFL SECONDARY LEARNERS

Ne'matova Umida Jumanazar qizi, master's student

*Absamatova Charos G'ayratovna, master's student
Shahrisabz State Pedagogical Institute*

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Annotation

This article discusses the lexical errors made by secondary school students in essay writing, their root causes, and practical solutions. Young learners' lack of experience in the language learning process, poor vocabulary, and the influence of their native language cause them to use contextually inappropriate words during the essay-writing process, which demands the implementation of comprehensive and effective explanatory work with students.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada o'rta maktab o'quvchilari tomonidan insho yozishda yo'l qo'yiladigan leksik xatolar, ularning kelib chiqish sabablari hamda amaliy yechimlar muhokama qilingan. Yosh o'rganuvchilarning til o'rganish jarayonidagi tajribasining kamligi, zaif lug'at boyligi hamda o'z ona tilining ta'siri ularning insho yozish jarayonida kontekstga mos bo'lmagan so'zlardan foydalanishiga sabab bo'ladi va bu o'quvchilarga to'liq va samarali tushuntirish ishlarini olib borilishini talab qiladi.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматриваются лексические ошибки, допускаемые учащимися средних школ при написании сочинений, причины их возникновения и практические решения. Недостаток опыта молодых учащихся в процессе изучения языка, слабый словарный запас и влияние родного языка приводят к использованию слов, не соответствующих контексту, в процессе написания сочинений, что требует проведения полной и эффективной разъяснительной работы с учащимися.

Learning a foreign language is a complex process that requires considerable time, effort and continuous practice. Language learners often struggle to develop fluency and master different language skills. Knowledge of the first language can sometimes support learners in understanding certain aspects of the target language, as some grammatical features such as word formation, subject-verb agreement, gender, and tense usage may show similarities across languages. Although learners may gradually become successful in applying grammatical rules in everyday communication, appropriate vocabulary usage in different contexts remains one of the most challenging aspects of language learning.

Among the four language skills, speaking and writing especially require learners to demonstrate a strong command of vocabulary and the ability to use words accurately and appropriately. Developing this ability takes a long period of practice and exposure to the language. Even after years of study, many learners continue to experience difficulties in selecting suitable words to express their thoughts and opinions effectively. In particular, secondary school EFL learners often struggle with lexical usage in essay writing. Therefore, vocabulary misuse in essays written by Uzbek EFL secondary learners can be considered an important area for research.

Secondary school learners, typically between grades 5 and 9, often struggle with a limited vocabulary. This frequently leads them to apply the word-usage rules of their first language to

Lisoniy meros va tilshunoslik taraqqiyoti

English, or to invent their own ways of expressing thoughts. Consequently, students often get stuck searching for the right word, which can lower their self-esteem.

One of the most common issues is 'wrong word choice.' For example, learners often confuse “homework” and “housework”, using the former to describe any task done at home. Furthermore, the richness of English collocations poses a significant challenge. Many Uzbek learners tend to overlook collocations, focusing only on individual words. As a result, they frequently make errors without realizing it—such as saying “strong rain” instead of “heavy rain”. Addressing these collocations is essential for helping students move toward natural fluency. In academic essays, learners often struggle with register, frequently using informal language—such as “kids” instead of “children” or “offspring”. This issue is often compounded by “L1 interference”, where students translate directly from their native language, leading to unnatural word choices (for example, “the last” is used instead of “the latest”).

Another significant hurdle is the repetitive use of “empty” adjectives. Instead of diversifying their vocabulary, students lean heavily on common words like good, beautiful and interesting. This lack of synonym variety not only makes the writing feel repetitive but also leads to lexical errors when a more precise term is required. Without a strong grasp of synonyms and formality, students find it difficult to convey complex ideas effectively in writing.

There may be several reasons for occurring errors in learning the second language. According to Brown, learners make some errors due to L1 interference, meaning that learners gets confused between two languages[1]. Brown states that when L2 learners in the beginner level have not yet learned much about L2; they tend to use the rules in the process like the native language” [2]. Bennui worked on and depicted aspects of L1 interference in students’ paragraph writing and found problems with lexicon since students translated words from L1 (Thai) to L2 (English)[3]. The lack of vocabulary causes the wrong translation and learners would rather interpret the ideas in the frame of the native language rules. Problems were also found with word order, subject-verb agreement, verb tense, prepositions, and noun determiners and these all happens due to L1 syntactic interference. In a similar way, Kırkgöz analyzed beginner students’ essays for punctuation and capitalization and found that their errors were mostly due to L1 (Turkish) interference[4]. Falhasiri, Tavakoli, Hasiri, and Mohammadzadeh also found that the most frequent errors resulted from L1 (Persian) interference, and the misuse of prepositions as the most frequent errors of interference [5].

In conclusion, most scholars studied how lexical errors are caused and how they can be prevented in writing essays. L1 interference is the main factor in vocabulary misuse as learners frequently translate directly from their first language. Therefore, a learner need enough time and a significant amount of effort to acquire how to express their ideas with right words in essays. Because in the early phase of the learning process most learners think less productively in English and have a tendency in expressing what they have in mind in the way of their native language. With several attempts the words and their usage are obtained by learners to use them effectively. As solutions I think implementing books on vocabulary teaching in the curriculum of the secondary education and explaining the ways of expressing ideas and translating into English properly to the pupils are necessary actions for both educators and learners.

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